

ESSENTIALITY OF KNOWING TRANSVERSAL COMPETENCIES: TOWARDS ENGINEERING EDUCATION SUSTAINABILITY AND INDUSTRY READINESS OF ENGINEERING STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Engineering education is to prepare engineers for real-world challenges and seek novel solutions to cater to society's different needs. There is an increase in the global demand for industry-ready engineers. Engineering education sustainability and industry readiness are mutually inclusive, where the former is the combination of different skills and transversal competencies, while the latter is all about their applicability. Transversal competencies, transferable across disciplines, chisel engineering students to become versatile and practical on the shop floor.

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Sustainability in engineering education is usually discussed only from the ecological/environmental viewpoints. This paper tries to find out the relevance of transversal competencies from the perspectives of engineering students at three levels: the most recurring competencies, the competencies they lack, and the ones that need improvement. Recurring and essential transversal competencies such as problem-solving, creativity and innovation, communication, lifelong learning etc., were identified from different policy frameworks of accreditation agencies, industry reports, organizational reports, and academia. Primary data was collected from final-year engineering students for this exploratory research through semi-structured interviews. These transversal competencies, latent throughout the formative years, have a definite role in the engineer's industry readiness, making engineering education sustainable. The need for industry readiness of the engineering students indicates the sustainability of engineering education, which can bridge the gap between the industry and academia. The paper reveals opportunities for further expansion of the competency frameworks in the policymaking and accreditation procedures.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The role of engineers in the world is significant. The world is developing every day and so is the concept of engineering. The world has successfully entered the phase of Engineering 5.0. The main concept in Engineering Education 5.0 is sustainable engineering, which refers to the implementation of engineering solutions without much hindrance to the environment using fewer resources and materials to enable the engineers to face unforeseen challenges (Lantada, 2020). According to the United Nations sustainable development goal 2030, engineers are the solvers of global challenges. Traditional education, which focuses on knowledge, cognition, and technical skills (Care, 2017), often in a pedagogic model, is not enough to keep pace with this multifaceted transformation in the industry. Hence, to prepare the engineers for sustainability, innovative approaches in the learning are rapidly increasing (Cropley 2015; Payzin, 2017). Engineering education is constantly evolving due to new technology and a changing global context. Therefore, learning needs to be active and learner-centred with the help of problem-based learning, project-based learning, research-based learning, etc. (Care, 2017). The learning process evokes behavioural attributes of the learner which work in combination with domain knowledge in the situated context. These learner-centred experiential processes are more effective than a lecture which does not include the participation of the learner (Crasovan, 2017; Cruz et al., 2019). The development of transversal competencies works through these experience-based learning processes.

1.2 Sustainable engineering education

Sustainability, reaching out to all disciplines and levels of engineering education at the university, is likely to extend into lifelong professional development (Lantada, 2020). The sustainability of engineering education depends upon the industry and

competency readiness of the engineer. In the engineering industry, the term industry readiness has different dimensions such as process, technology, and organisation. Industry readiness at the engineering graduate level is dependent on the workforce learning and development, leadership, and transversal competencies (Devika et al., 2020). To address the current changes and future challenges across the engineering industries, there is a call for more explorations in sustainable engineering education.

The level of different competencies and interdisciplinary discourses affects the industry readiness of the graduated engineers (Murugesan et al., 2021). There are many definitions, frameworks, and categorisations of transversal competencies by accreditation agencies, international organisations, academicians, and employers. All these domains have overlapping, recurring, and shifting patterns which are defined by the scope of the respective studies/documents (Devika et al., 2021). The needs and objectives of engineering education are already well defined. But there is a need to integrate and work with other disciplines to form a sustainable engineering education platform which is the current need. In engineering education 5.0, the focus has also shifted to the practical part where both domain and theoretical knowledge rely on/are supported by the sub-skills and competencies to attain the desired result. The key stakeholders in this process are the engineering students. For these reasons, a key element of transformed engineering education is that it addresses the sustainability of its human resources: the engineer individually and the engineering community collectively. Crucial to such a transformed engineering education will be the incorporation of elements to help graduate engineers maintain and enhance their abilities over their careers and to adapt to future times and conditions (Sulej, 2021).

In this paper, the meaning of sustainable engineering education is broadened to include the sustainability of the engineer's lifelong learning. The paper tries to analyse the awareness of final year engineering students about transversal competencies at three levels: the most important competencies, the competencies they lack, and the competencies which need improvements.

2 METHODOLOGY

The study has used qualitative research design. Interview was conducted to collect data using a semi-structured schedule as an instrument. Using relevant literature from academia, accreditation agencies documents, industry reports, and project reports and organisational reports, recurring and important transversal competencies in engineering education were narrowed down to creativity and innovation, communication, teamwork, lifelong learning, problem-solving, ethics and environmental awareness. To identify the importance and use of these six transversal competencies, semi-structured interviews were conducted with thirty-five final year engineering students at BITS, Pilani, India. The questions for the semi-structured schedule were prepared with the help of education experts, research scholars, relevant literature and engineering graduates who have extensive industry experience. The interviews were conducted in two phases. Prior to the interviews, the respondents were properly oriented with specialised guidelines. In the first phase, the use, awareness, and purpose of the selected transversal competencies

were asked to the students. In the second phase, they were asked to rank and arrange these competencies at three levels; competencies that are important, lacking, and need improvements. For the data analysis, the interviews were audio and videotaped for better documentation and clarity which were later transcribed word-for-word. Content analysis approach (Krippendorff, 2013) was used for data analysis using MAXQDA software (see Table 1). The inter-rater-reliability of the competencies was 0.95 which is considered as a strong value.

3 RESULTS

Based on the content analysis results from the first phase of the interviews, the six transversal competencies (theme), considered important by the final year students – teamwork, communication, creativity and innovation, problem-solving, ethics and environmental awareness, and life-long learning – were extracted from codes via category. The table 1 shows the absolute and relative coding identified for the use of these transversal competencies by the students.

The students were also asked to rank the competencies to gauge the importance of these competencies as per their knowledge. The students ranked problem solving, required to face the uncertainties, as the most important competency followed by innovation and creativity, communication, teamwork, lifelong learning, and ethics-social and environment awareness. Students thought that they needed improvement in communication, teamwork, and lifelong learning; they were aware but lacked the applicability of ethics and environment awareness. The students had the understanding that problem solving abilities, acquired over the period of graduation, would help them at the workplace. For innovation and creativity, communication, teamwork, lifelong learning, and ethics-social and environment awareness, many of the students acknowledged the importance of practice schools (shop floor visits) and internships which would help them to assess and use the other competencies. The study revealed that although the students were aware about the environment impact and ethics in the engineering fields, the knowledge was only peripheral. Students were aware of the need for the competencies which would make them industry ready. But the students were unaware of the identification and integration of the competencies when they faced a problem.

Table 1. Use of transversal competencies by the final year students

Transversal Competency Domain (Theme)	Category	Codes	Coding absolute: the number of codes identified by students/ the total number of codes extracted from the literature review	Coding relative: %
Problem Solving	Problem Identification	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• critical thinking• holistic problem approach• clarity	62/62	100

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • observation 		
	Cognition (Application)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • possible outcomes notion • decision making • concepts clarity • differences identification • comprehension 	64/70	91.42
	Reflection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • finding similarities/unique ness • learning from errors 	60/60	100
Innovation and Creativity	Motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • challenge • freedom • idea support and idea time • motivation • cognitive abilities • thinking style • knowledge 	50/59	84.74
	Idea Generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • intelligence and curiosity • autonomy • hard work and perseverance • technical resources • openness 	41/50	82
	Reflection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • flexibility • encouragement and recognition • challenge and pressure • risk taking 	39/50	78
Communication	Presentation Skills and Client Interaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • feedback • ideas sharing 	48/67	71.64

	Intercultural Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • experience field/area • self-confidence • self-exposure 	42/59	71.18
	Team Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • listening and reading • cooperation • mutual responsibility • shared field of experiences 	40/54	74.07
Teamwork	Leadership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • agreement • authority • accountability • trust • adaptability • decision making methods 	60/77	77.92
	Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • clarity • direction • shared purpose • individuality 	44/57	77.19
	Workflow Procedures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • dedication • working relationship • conflict management 	52/73	71.23
Lifelong Learning	Initiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • engagement • motivation and curiosity to learn • willingness 	50/65	76.92
	Learning Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • self-efficacy beliefs • empowerment • learning (study plan) • intellectual development • information location and scrutinisation 	46/62	74.19

	Reflection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • self-reflection, self-monitoring, self-regulation • satisfaction • metacognition 	46/62	74.19
Awareness on Ethics and Environment	Environment and Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • responsibility towards environment • knowledge on health hazards 	20/37	54.05
	Awareness on Ethics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • commitment • job value • integrity 	17/35	48.57
	Application of the Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • offer constructive criticism • treat everyone with respect • heed critical reviews 	15/35	42.85

4 DISCUSSION

The responses from the interviews revealed that each competency had its relevance at each stage. These competencies work in relation to each other. The domain knowledge is to be strengthened with the process knowledge as well. Exposure to organisation and its working creates the environment to learn the competencies at the scale of real task execution. These transversal competencies are relevant in multiple ways (see Table 1). Competencies are not flat or unidimensional but dynamic and multidimensional. An explicit exposure and experience seems to create an understanding which may help them implement these competencies more effectively. Theoretical understanding about the process gets challenged and fine-tuned by the real work with people from different academic backgrounds, cultural sensibilities, communication ease, etc. The terminologies take different understandings when put in the context of real-life situations/industries/workplace. The learning turns out to be lifelong and life wide.

According to the study, students tend to learn more from errors and try to remember and not repeat the same in a similar problem. By the final year of graduation, the students develop their own ways of problem solving. Problem identification, cognition, and reflection, the components of problem solving, are most sought after by the final year engineering students. To solve the problem, the students are expected to include experiences of other people. Hence, teamwork plays an

important role in it. Teamwork includes leadership, communication in the team, workflow procedures. The values reflect that teamwork is one of the areas the students think that they need improvement and many of them think that this can only be achieved when they are in a real team in the industry. The students who had industry internships suggested that they needed more such practice-based learning methods in engineering education. The team can only work in a comprehensive manner if the team members are engaged in active communication. Communication also contributes to other competencies as well, such as teamwork, where the students are concerned about the linguistic capabilities and clarity in the oral presentation of ideas. The data suggests that the intercultural communication competence also needs to be improved while student interaction in the teams is better compared to the other components of communication. Innovation and creativity is one of the competency domains the students are well aware of. In the formative years of graduation, they get the opportunities and freedom for innovation. The students think that the education gives more space for them to think creatively and to come up with novel ideas and solutions. In the process of innovation and creativity, final year students use motivation, idea generation, and reflection. For them, motivation is the most used part of innovation and creativity followed by idea generation and reflection. Most of them think that they need more freedom and flexibility to work innovatively, a concern once they are placed in an industry.

As the industries are expanding their reach in terms of ethics and environment awareness, the least preferred competency domain by the students. The students know the environmental sustainability of a particular product or process, theoretically. But they think many times before applying the knowledge. They are more profit conscious and would consider the economy and profit parameters before thinking about sustainability. Ethical perspectives are yet to be developed for the final year students as they have only some general information on the domain.

Many of the students expect to cover these competencies in the upcoming training programs once they are placed. They are aware but need the exposure to industry to see the application of competencies at the workplace. The learning scope is wide and varied with no-definite and no-fixed notions.

5 SUMMARY

The awareness, use, and integration of transversal competencies from the formative years help the holistic development of the engineers. This sustainability in engineering education can only be achieved only when the transversal competencies are identified and used according to the needs by the students. As a first step, this study identified and classified the transversal competencies according to the perspective of engineering graduates. Following, learning from, and using an integrated framework of transversal competencies may help learners attain industry readiness and engineering education sustainability.

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